

BB-2208 Human Resource Management

Individual Assignment 2: Multiple case study analysis

Case study: Ayesha's Farm

HRM Model: Standard Casual model of HRM

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Introduction:

Human Resource Management as defined by Armstrong (2006) is a coherent and strategic approach on how to manage an organization's valued assets. In other words, strategic and coherent approaches on how to manage development and employment of people (Armstrong and Taylor, 2014) This essay will focus on the case study of Ayesha's Farm and how can the standard casual human resource management model applied to the business, discussion weather the model is suitable to be used in detecting issues in businesses and what affects it has on Ayesha's Farm as well as recommendations on what can be done to improve or ease the issue of the business.

Ayesha's Farm:

As written by Musa, Pg Hj Idris and Basir (2020) Ayesha's Farm is a small part-time basis agricultural business owned by a husband and wife which centers around growing hydroponic plants. Located in the residential area of Lugu, this small business which started at the end of 2017 also sells hydroponic sets to people for personal use (Musa, Pg Hj Idris and Basir,2020). The small farm also offers farming lessons to children with the goal to have them interested in the field of agriculture and to show locals on how to be self-sufficient (Musa, Pg Hj Idris and Basir, 2020).

The produced harvested are either for self-consumption, given away or sold to potential customers at a rate of one or two dollars per 100 grams (Musa, Pg Hj Idris and Basir, 2020).

The sets sold either costs 150 dollars to 200 dollars with servicing and the couples would regularly update on their customers so that these sets would function properly and stays in excellent shape (Musa, Pg Hj Idris and Basir, 2020). Often, their business would receive school trips as educators have shown interest in implementing hydroponic system in school.

Challenges of Ayesha's Farm:

As stated in Musa, Pg Hj Idris and Basir (2020) the challenges faced by Ayesha's Farm are as follows:

1. Any produce that they have harvested are not sold to local shops as they are not certain if they can handle with the demand due to their business being small.
2. The husband can only give his dedication to the business during the weekends or late evenings due to time constraints in which he reaches home around 6 or 7 evening.
3. Financial problems in terms of money as the profit earned from the business are spent on paying energy and water bills as well as getting supplies.

4. A limited amount of space as they are currently farming using their backyard.

Standard casual model of Human resource management:

The standard casual model of human resource management shows relationship between human resource management and performance. An illustration example the standard casual model of human resource management taken from Guest, Paauwe and Wright (2013) is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1.

According to Guest, Paauwe and Wright (2013) the model describes it is frequently accepted that financial performances are not directly influenced by Human Resource practices. Under HRM outcomes, it is said that the human resource practices have a more direct impact on a worker's behavior and attitude (Guest, Paauwe and Wright, 2013). In the internal performance panel, Guest, Paauwe and Wright (2013) states that operational organizational performance are affected by changes. Changes in an employee's knowledge, abilities and skills can influence Internal performance, in this case, the unmediated HRM effect within the simple human resource management model, while and increase or decrease in internal performance will either contribute to a higher or lower level of organizational performance (Guest, Paauwe and Wright, 2013).

Identifying Root Cause using Standard casual model of Human Resource Management:

In Ayesha's farm there are 3 main problems: Time, Space and Finance.

Time management status as explained by Agrawal (2010) determines whether an "employee's time data is evaluated by time evaluation or not." The time constraint problem in Ayshea's farm mentioned in Musa, Pg Hj Idris and Basir (2020) is regarding tending the farm on late evenings. The space problem as implied by Musa, Pg Hj Idris and Basir (2020) under challenges is the unavailability of larger areas for farming. Referring back to the standard casual HRM model, to improve financial performance, the farm must need to improve its internal performances. However, in order to do so, they may require the right HR strategy and HR practices. Under practices, time management needs to be improved whereas under strategy needs a solution for their farm's space problems. By following the standard casual human resource management model, this should lead to a better human resource outcome, therefore improved internal performance which would eventually lead to improved financial performance.

Issues of Standard casual model of Human Resource Management:

Despite identifying the root issues using the standard casual model of human resource management, there are several issues regarding the standard casual model of human resource management itself. Firstly, the standard casual model of human resource management, assumes that an organization's strategic objectives may either be believed that Human Resource Model is develop in response to objectives or to prescribe the Human Resource management input which either way, human resource management pursues a downstream from overall strategy of an organization. However, Boselie, Dietz and Boon (2005) believes that the said statement may not always be true. As taken from Wood, there is a strong suggestion from resource-based views that Human Resource Management strategy may follow an upstream of a product market strategy (as cited in Boselie, Dietz and Boon, 2005) thus leading to implication by Boselie, Dietz and Boon (2005) that presently, a little is known in regards to the impact of Human Resource Management on strategic-decision making. Therefore, in the case of this case study, identifying the root problems may not have much impact for a desirable outcome.

Human Resource Management interventions derived from Human resource strategy understood to bring about rise in the outcomes related to Human Resource management. According to Boselie, Dietz and Boon (2005) within the model itself, it implies that good behavior and attitudes from employees will result in good internal performance, such as shown in figure one.

However, that is not necessarily the case. Boselie, Dietz and Boon (2005) illustrates that interventions in job design, training and performance management may improve a workers effectiveness weather it its trough their technical knowledge, abilities and skills or removing task- related obstacles to improve performance, either way it will still not change their HRM related behaviors and attitudes.

Another issue in regards to the standard casual model human resource management according to Boselie, Dietz and Boon (2005) is that the model neglects empirical studies of human resource management interventions taken from human resource strategy which are understood to give rise in Human resource related outcomes.

Recommendation to the issues in Ayesha's Farm:

Trough research, the following can be recommended to each of the issues founded in Ayshea's farm:

To relief space problems, which they are currently using their backyard to farm (Musa, Pg Hj Idris and Basir, 2020) there is a solution that could be worth to consider. For produces that are planted for self-consumption, consider doing indoor hydroponics. In an article by Miller (2018), states that indoor hydroponics which are grown inside buildings that may or may not have windows uses LED-lighting. Therefore, making use of indoor space, such as kitchen counters, windowsills, or an empty room, may help with growing more produce. However, it is worth noting that use of LED lights can be costly (Miller,2018).

While time management needs an improvement, the husband's time constraint is unchangeable as he the main cause of his time constraint is his main job. The recommendation for this, in the based under Human Resource terms would be compressed workweek. As explained by Mayhew (2017) a compressed work schedule permits worker to complete a task a week fewer than five days. In Mayhew's (2017) example, rather than working at 9 a.m. to 6 p.m. from Monday to Friday, with the compressed work schedule, workers can work Monday through Thursday or Tuesday trough Friday from 7 a.m. to 6 p.m. In Ayesha's farm's case, instead of tending the farm on late evenings every week as stated in Musa, Pg Hj Idris and Basir (2020), depending on the schedule of the husband's main job, on some of his working days, he can tend the farm early or before he goes to work. As stated by Mayhew (2017) "it may be difficult to manage a workforce on compressed schedule, however, staggered schedules can ensure adequate coverage".

However, because there are issues in the standard casual model of human resource management itself, it is not clear that solving the two main issues above will ease their financial worries, therefore it is recommended that money management should be practiced. As explained by Chen (2019) money management is the process of investing, budgeting, saving, spending, or otherwise overseeing capital usage of groups or individuals. It can also be referred narrowly to “portfolio management” or “investment management” (Chen,2019).

Conclusion:

In conclusion the standard casual model of human resource management is just one out of several human resource models that may help the firm detect the roots of their management issues, however through innovations, better solutions can be made to ease current issues.

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